

XPS

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 182.**

Call NMBP-26-2016

Gracious: Grant agreement

Deliverable:

Deliverable

Work Package:

Delivery date: January 27th, 2020

Lead Beneficiary:

Nature of Deliverable: SOP

Dissemination Level: Public

Submitted by:	F.Fumagalli, D. Comandella
Revised by:	G. Ceccone
Approved by:	H. Rauscher

Document Control Page	
Deliverable Title	SOP for XPS analysis of nanoparticles in powder and suspension form
Author (writer/editor and short name of the participant)	Daniele Comandella
Short Description (e.g. abstract, summary, table of contents, free text etc.)	This document should work as Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) for the sample preparation and surface analysis of nanoparticles via XPS
Publisher (e.g. journal publisher or the consortium)	consortium
Contributors (co-authors with participant short name)	Daniele Comandella, Francesco Fumagalli
Nature (peer-reviewed article, technical report, table, prototype, demonstrator, etc.)	SOP
Creation date	20/01/2020
Version number	2
Version date (dd/mm/yyyy)	24/01/2020
Last modified by (person and organisation name)	Giacomo Ceccone
Rights (e.g. Intellectual Property Rights, copyright, such as copyright "ACEnano consortium")	Gracious Consortium
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU = Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

	<input type="checkbox"/> RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) <input type="checkbox"/> CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
Review status	Where applicable: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Accepted for publication <input type="checkbox"/> Date of publication
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by Partners involved in the preparation of the document <input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by all Gracious partners <input type="checkbox"/> for approval by the WP leader <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for approval by the Project Coordinator
Requested deadline (dd/mm/yyyy)	

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
V1	20/01/2020	Daniele Comandella, Francesco Fumagalli	Creation
V2	24/01/2020	Giacomo Ceccone	Revision
V3			
V4			

Standard Operating Procedure

Title: XPS analysis of nanoparticles in powder and suspension form

Contents

- 1 Scope and application**
 - 2 Terms, definitions and normative references**
 - 3 Abbreviated terms**
 - 4 Method principle**
 - 5 Safety procedures and precautions**
 - 6 Procedure**
 - 6.1 Apparatus and equipment
 - 6.2 Chemicals, materials and reagents
 - 6.3 Samples
 - 6.4 Performing measurements
 - 6.4.1 Operation of the equipment
 - 6.4.2 Sample preparation
 - 6.4.3 Measurement description
 - 6.4.4 Data analysis
 - 7 Calculation of results**
 - 8 Quality control**
 - 9 Measurement uncertainty and traceability**
 - 10 Reporting of results**
 - 11 Validation status**
 - 12 Literature references**
- Annexes**
- Document change history and approval**

1. Scope and application

The scope of this SOP is to provide a description of the methodology to be used for the application of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) to the analysis of nanoparticles both in powder and suspension form.

XPS will provide:

- 1) Average surface composition of nanoparticles
- 2) Surface chemistry of different elements
- 3) Composition and average thickness of eventual organic coating present.

This SOP has been applied to several type of nanoparticles amongst which, SiO₂, TiO₂, CeO₂, Au...

2. Terms, definitions and normative references

The normative references are reported in the chapter 12, whilst the abbreviation are defined in chapter 3.

3. Abbreviated terms

XPS: X-ray Photoelectron spectroscopy

ToF-SIMS: Time of Flight Secondary Emission Spectrometry

IPD: Individual Protective Devices

RSF: Relative Sensitivity factor

FWHM: Full Width Half Maximum

4. Method principle

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is a surface analysis technique used for analysing the surface chemistry of a material. XPS can measure the elemental composition, empirical formula, chemical state and electronic state of the elements within a material. XPS spectra are obtained by illuminating a solid surface with a beam of X-rays -monochromatic or unfiltered Al K α or Mg K α - while simultaneously measuring the kinetic energy and electrons that are emitted from the top 1-10 nm of the material, thereby originating a XPS spectrum. The position and intensity of the peaks in the spectrum provide the desired chemical state and quantitative information. A typical XPS spectrum is then a plot of the number of electrons detected (sometimes per unit time) (Y-axis, ordinate) versus the binding energy of the electrons detected (X-axis, abscissa). Each element produces a characteristic set of XPS peaks at characteristic binding energy values that directly identify each element that exists in or on the surface of the material being analysed. These

characteristic spectral peaks correspond to the electron configuration of the electrons within the atoms, e.g., 1s, 2s, 2p, 3s, etc. The number of detected electrons in each of the characteristic peaks is directly related to the amount of element within the XPS sampling volume

5. Safety procedures and precautions

See chapter 6.

6. Procedure

The goal of this section is to identify all relevant steps and the resources needed to accomplish the procedures, such as method calibration, sample preparation and analysis, data acquisition, etc.

6.1 Apparatus and equipment

List of items required

- Pellet press
 - Micropipettes and tips
 - Powder-free and Si-free gloves
 - metallic tweezers
 - Powder mask
 - Protective goggles
 - Double-stick copper or carbon tape
 - Sample stage (bar-type sample holder, 10.5 x 1.5 cm)
 - Cup-type sample holder (1 x 1 cm)
 - Fume hood for hazardous materials
 - Conductive flat supports: silicon (Si) wafers or gold-coated Si wafer (area $\approx 1 \times 1$ cm). The choice of the support depends on the physicochemical characteristics of the material to be analyzed.
 - XPS spectrometer: e.g. AXIS Ultra DLD, Kratos Analytical, UK
- Acquisition and analysis Software package: e.g. Vision 2 (Kratos analytical) for data acquisition and CasaXPS-v2.23 (<http://www.casaxps.com/>) for data analysis.

6.2 Chemicals, reference materials and reagents

The following chemicals, materials and reagents are required

-Acetone (CH₃)₂CO CAS 67-64-1

-Ethanol CH₃CH₂OH CAS 64-17-5

-Hexane CH₃(CH₂)₄CH₃ CAS 110-54-3

-Clean Al foils

-Sample storage:

-Powders should be stored in sealed glass bottles, possibly in dark, room temperature and low humidity conditions (if not otherwise specified)

Minimizing or better avoiding contact with atmosphere to reduce contamination is advisable.

Use of individual protection devices (IPD) equipment is required

6.3 Samples

Samples to be analysed could be in dry form or in suspension. The amounts usually needed for the analysis are:

- Dry nanoparticles: 1-5 mg depending on dimensions and material type
- Suspensions: 100-200 µL depending on concentration

6.4 Performing measurements

6.4.1 Operation of the equipment

The XPS spectrometer should be calibrated following either the recommended ISO procedure or other documented procedures used in the laboratory. The energy scale calibration is normally carried out using clean Cu, Au and Ag samples (foils or thin films), whilst the quantitative calibration can be obtained by the analysis of a clean Teflon and/or gold sample.

6.4.2 Sample preparation

There are few accepted methods of sample preparation. Generally speaking, the material is deposited on a flat surface, achieving layers that are 0.5 - 1 cm² in size and up to 4 mm thick. Routine XPS measurements have an 8 – 10 nm probing depth, but a larger thickness is needed to avoid interference from the support. Powders may be dissolved in a suitable solvent and then drop cast onto the surface of a flat support such as clean silicon wafer. Alternatively, powders be either sprinkled onto the surface of sticky tape (carbon or copper-based) or pressed into a tablets for analysis. Sample preparation should also lead to well-attached and uniform layers: powders migrating through the XPS vacuum system is potentially very destructive to the instrument and should be avoided. Sample preparation and handling should be conducted avoiding contamination. Therefore, use gloves and clean tweezers, work under the hood and transfer the samples storing them in a close environment, such as a Petri dish.

Hereafter steps for sample preparation are reported

6.4.2.1 Powder samples

- Press powder (usually few mg) into pellets by using the pellet press. Do not apply too much force which might result in change of material properties. Do not use any binding agent (e.g. ethanol) because it can modify the surface conditions.
- Place the pellet onto a copper tape on the sample stage. The bar-type sample stage can fit up to 8 samples of minimal size. You might want to use some aluminium foil to gently press the pellet to improve attachment to the foil.
- Then, insert it into the XPS pre-loading vacuum chamber.
- For powders that pose a health hazard if inhaled (such as multi-walled carbon nanotubes MWCNTs): work under a fume hood and press the material directly into copper tape hosted into a cup-sized holder. Remove the non-attached material and carefully transfer the sample cup to the XPS vacuum chamber.
- Clean all used equipment with acetone, ethanol and hexane before preparing the following sample.

6.4.2.2 Suspended materials

The sample preparation involves depositing the material as thin film on a flat support. Any technique depositing thin layers with the required area and thickness (0.5 - 1 cm² and up to 4 mm, respectively) can be used. Due to its easy use and low waste of material, this protocol focuses on *drop casting*.

- First, prepare a slurry by dispersing the material in a suitable solvent. The chosen solvent should not dissolve the material and evaporate relatively quickly (so acetone, ethanol, water are usually employed). The dispersion concentration should ensure good attachment of the material to the

support and uniform distribution. As it depends on the properties of material and support, it should be determined on a case-by-case basis.

-Properly clean the selected flat support. For Si wafer or Au-coated Si wafer, a procedure for cleaning could be washing the support with various solvents (water, hexane, acetone, and ethanol) in consecutive steps. Dry the supports under argon or nitrogen flow.

-Deposit a 10ul droplet of dispersion on the flat support and keep it under vacuum to achieve solvent evaporation. Repeat until the desired thickness is achieved.

-Stick the support onto an adhesive tape (copper or carbon-based) on a bar-type sample holder and transfer it to the XPS vacuum chamber.

6.4.3 Measurement description

Before measurement, samples should be degassed by keeping them under high vacuum. For Axis Ultra DLD Kratos Analytical instrument, the lowest recommended pressure before proceeding is 9×10^{-7} bar. To count the number of electrons during the acquisition of a spectrum with a minimum of error, XPS detectors must be operated under ultra-high vacuum conditions because electron counting detectors in XPS instruments are typically one meter away from the material irradiated with X-rays. After reaching the desired pressure, transfer the sample bar into the storage analyser chamber.

Below a short description of the XPS measurement steps related to the Axis Ultra-DLD spectrometer.

Please note that in case of different spectrometer the settings should be adapted.

-Selection of spots on sample surface

This is achieved by activating the X-ray gun, moving across the surface and selecting spots yielding the highest signal/noise ratio of a selected peak in the XPS spectrum. To this end, either a characteristic peak of the sample (if known) or the C1s peak at 285 eV is commonly used, as most of samples have hydrocarbons adsorbed onto their surface. Spots without any signal or originating broad peaks should not be chosen.

-Measurement settings

Measurement settings depend on the type of material being analysed and the desired analysis goals. If the objective is to evaluate surface elemental compositions, the following settings can be used:

X-Ray gun: Monochromatic Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV), 150 W

Neutraliser: active, energy of electrons = 20 eV

Analysed area: 400x700 μm^2

Scan type: survey (wide)

-Data acquisition settings

Survey: energy range (0-1200eV), pass energy (80-160 eV), dwell time (120ms), energy step (1eV), number of scans (1-2)). Minimum three different positions per sample must be analysed.

If the goal is to obtain information about the chemical state of the different elements present at the sample surface, typical data acquisition settings are reported below:

Energy range (depends on the element), pass energy (20 or 40eV), dwell time (120ms), energy step (0.05eV), number of scans (2-3). A minimum of two positions per sample must be analysed.

In case of high level of contaminants (hydrocarbons) present at the surface, a cleaning procedure by ion etching could be used. However, because of sample damage and preferential sputtering of light elements careful selection of the etching parameters is needed.

In the case of Axis Ultra DLD equipped with Minibeam 1 ion gun and for inorganics samples (e.g. SiO₂), the following settings could be employed:

Ar⁺ ions @ 2KeV,

Area: 5x5mm²

Sample current about 1-1.5μA

Etching time: 2-5 min

6.4.4 Data Analysis

Spectra acquired with the XPS instruments should be saved and opened with a specific data analysis software that allows peak identification and quantification, such as CasaXPS (<http://www.casaxps.com/>). A very concise description of the main evaluation actions is shown in this paragraph. Please refer to the software manual for an extensive description of software functioning

(for CasaXPS: <https://mmrc.caltech.edu/XPS%20software/CASA/Books/CasaXPS%20User%20Guide.pdf>)

Identification is usually achieved through libraries containing a list of elements with the corresponding binding energy. An offset in binding energies can occur in absence of neutralisation.

7. Calculation of results

Raw data obtained with the acquisition software are transformed in VAMAS files (.vms), which includes description of the conditions used for the analysis. The vms files are analysed using the CasaXPS software v2.23. Surface compositions are obtained from the wide (survey) spectra using RSF provided by the manufacturer (Kratos Analytical). The core level spectra are fitted using asymmetric Lorentian functions after a Tougaard background subtraction.

8. Quality control

The quality of the measurements can be assessed by interlaboratory investigations and exercises following VAMAS (<http://www.vamas.org/>) and Euramet (<https://www.euramet.org/>) protocols and procedures. Furthermore analysis of corresponding samples not in nano-form (e.g. homogenous thin films) could be of help to reduce errors in data interpretation. Finally, for the quantitative analysis a minimum of three position for each samples must be analysed. If this is not possible using normal set-up, small area analysis and Photoemission images to identify suitable analysis areas are advisable.

9. Measurement uncertainty and traceability

The error in the quantitative analysis provided by XPS is estimated to be 10%, whilst the resolution of the spectrometer and the correspondent minimum chemical shift depend upon the spectrometer type and the exciting source (monochromatic or not). In case of monochromatic Al-K α radiation ($h\nu=1486.6$ eV), the energy resolution is of the order of 40-60meV (FWHM of the Au4f7/2 peak).

10. Reporting of results

The results obtained could be reported in Excel (2016) or Origin (OriginPro 2015) table, whilst fitted spectra can be exported as txt files for plotting or saved as images in bmp or jpg format.

A template for data reports is available in most analysis software packages.

11. Validation status

in house

12. Literature references

- 1) *D. Briggs & M.P. Seah (eds), Practical Surface Analysis vol 1, 1983, Wiley Ltd, UK*
- 2) *D. Briggs and J.T. Grant (eds), Surface analysis by Auger and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy, 2003, Surface Spectra (IM publication, UK)*
- 3) *J.C. Vickermann and I.S. Gilmore (eds), Surface Analysis: The Principal Techniques, 2009, Wiley Ltd*
- 4) *D.R. Bear et al., Preparation of nanoparticles for surface analysis In "Characterisation of Nanoparticles: measurements and Processes" V-D Hodoroaba, W.E.S. Unger, A.G. Shard (eds), 2020, Elsevier Inc*
- 5) *ISO/TC 201/SC 2: Surface Chemical Analysis - Guide to sample handling, preparation and mounting - Part 1 - Guidelines to handling of specimens prior to analysis, 2017*
- 6) *ISO/TC 201/SC 2: Surface Chemical Analysis – Guide to sample handling, preparation and mounting – Part 2 Guide to preparation and mounting of specimens for analysis, 2017*
- 7) *ISO/TC 201/SC 2: Surface Chemical Analysis - Sample handling, preparation and mounting - Part 4 – reporting information related to the history, preparation, handling and mounting of nano-objects prior to surface analysis, 2017*
- 8) *R.D. Baer, et al., Biointerphases 11, 04B401 (2016); doi: 10.1116/1.4964867*
- 9) *R.D. Baer et al., Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A 37, 031401 (2019); doi: 10.1116/1.5065501*
- 10) *ISO15472:2010(en) Surface chemical analysis — X-ray photoelectron spectrometers — Calibration of energy scales*

Document approval

Approval by:

Date	Name	Job title	Signature
------	------	-----------	-----------

--	--	--	--